

Derivation of an analytic model of vibrational relaxation of CO₂ (a technical note)

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The model considered here describes the pump up of vibrational energy after rapid increase of translational-rotational temperature T as this may happen behind the shock fronts and in sound waves. The derivation of the corresponding energy relaxation equation for molecules which have only one mode of oscillation can be found in [1], Chapter 19. Here the derivation of [1] is generalized for CO₂ which has 3 modes of oscillation v_1, v_2, v_3 . The mode v_2 is double degenerate and has rotational momentum l : v_2^l .

Assumptions:

1. The molecule is a linear (harmonic) oscillator. Vibrational energy of the molecule:

$$E_v = \hbar\omega_1 v_1 + \hbar\omega_2 v_2 + \hbar\omega_3 v_3$$

2. Only the Vibrational-Translational (VT) transfer from the mode v_2^l is taken into account
3. The number of vibrational states is infinite

Since in the harmonic oscillator approximation E_v does not depend on the ro-vibrational momentum l of the bending modes the states with same v_2 and different l can be gathered into a combined state. There are $v_2 + 1$ different l possible for a fixed v_2 . The normalized matrix elements X of all possible VT-transitions are summarized in [2], Eq. (27) there:

$$\begin{aligned} v_2^l &\rightarrow (v_2 - 1)^{l+1}, & X &= v_2 - l \\ v_2^l &\rightarrow (v_2 - 1)^{l-1}, & X &= v_2 + l \\ v_2^l &\rightarrow (v_2 + 1)^{l+1}, & X &= v_2 + l + 2 \end{aligned}$$

$$v_2^l \rightarrow (v_2 + 1)^{l-1}, \quad X = v_2 - l + 2$$

The averaged probability of transition between combined states v_2 and $v_2 - 1$ is proportional to:

$$p_{v_2 \rightarrow v_2 - 1} \sim \frac{\sum_l \left(p_{v_2^l \rightarrow (v_2 - 1)^{l+1}} + p_{v_2^l \rightarrow (v_2 - 1)^{l-1}} \right)}{\sum_l 1} = \frac{\sum_l (v_2 - l + v_2 + l)}{\sum_l 1} \sim \frac{\sum_l v_2}{\sum_l 1}$$

$$p_{v_2 \rightarrow v_2 - 1} \sim v_2 \quad (1)$$

The sum \sum_l is taken over all values of l allowed for the corresponding v_2 . Between combined states v_2 and $v_2 + 2$:

$$p_{v_2 \rightarrow v_2 + 1} \sim \frac{\sum_l \left(p_{v_2^l \rightarrow (v_2 + 1)^{l+1}} + p_{v_2^l \rightarrow (v_2 + 1)^{l-1}} \right)}{\sum_l 1} = \frac{\sum_l (v_2 + l + 2 + v_2 - l + 2)}{\sum_l 1}$$

$$p_{v_2 \rightarrow v_2 + 1} \sim \frac{\sum_l (v_2 + 2)}{\sum_l 1} = v_2 + 2 \quad (2)$$

Some transitions which appear in the sums are not possible. For example the transition from $v_2^{v_2}$ to $(v_2 - 1)^{v_2 + 1}$ is not possible because this latter state does not exist. Such transitions must not be excluded explicitly from the sums because the formulas for X automatically give zero in those cases.

The particle balance equations for the number densities n of the combined vibrational states (v_1, v_2, v_3) reads as follows:

$$\frac{dn_{v_1 v_2 v_3}}{dt} = k_{v_2 + 1 \rightarrow v_2} n_{v_1 v_2 + 1 v_3} + k_{v_2 - 1 \rightarrow v_2} n_{v_1 v_2 - 1 v_3} -$$

$$- (k_{v_2 \rightarrow v_2 - 1} + k_{v_2 \rightarrow v_2 + 1}) n_{v_1 v_2 v_3}, \quad v_2 > 0 \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{dn_{v_1 0 v_3}}{dt} = k_{10} n_{v_1 1 v_3} - k_{01} n_{v_1 0 v_3} \quad (4)$$

Here k are the transition rates. The coefficients k_{10} and k_{01} are connected by the detailed balance (w is the degeneracy of the vibrational level):

$$\frac{k_{01}}{k_{10}} = \frac{n_1^{eq}}{n_0^{eq}} = \frac{w_1}{w_0} \exp\left(-\frac{E_1 - E_0}{T}\right) = 2 \exp\left(-\frac{\hbar\omega_2}{T}\right)$$

$$\frac{k_{01}}{k_{10}} = 2K, \quad K = \exp\left(-\frac{\hbar\omega_2}{T}\right) \quad (5)$$

Here w_i is the degeneracy of the vibrational level, n_i^{eq} is the number density of the component in thermodynamic equilibrium.

All the other rate coefficients can be connected with k_{10} using the expressions (1), (2) and (5):

$$k_{v_2 \rightarrow v_2 - 1} = v_2 k_{10}, \quad k_{v_2 \rightarrow v_2 + 1} = \frac{v_2 + 2}{2} k_{01} = (v_2 + 2) K k_{10} \quad (6)$$

$$k_{v_2 + 1 \rightarrow v_2} = (v_2 + 1) k_{10}, \quad k_{v_2 - 1 \rightarrow v_2} = (v_2 - 1 + 2) k_{01} = (v_2 + 1) K k_{10} \quad (7)$$

Equations (6), (7) are substituted into equations (3), (4). For convenience, indexes v_1, v_2, v_3 are replaced by i, j, k respectively. The resulting master equations read:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dn_{ijk}}{dt} = & k_{10} (j + 1) n_{ij+1k} + k_{10} K (j + 1) n_{ij-1k} - \\ & - k_{10} j n_{ijk} - k_{10} K (j + 2) n_{ijk}, \quad j > 0 \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

$$\frac{dn_{i0k}}{dt} = k_{10} n_{i1k} - 2K k_{10} n_{i0k} \quad (9)$$

To obtain the energy relaxation equation the equations (8) and (9) are multiplied by:

$$E_v = \hbar\omega_1 i + \hbar\omega_2 j + \hbar\omega_3 k = E_{ik} + \hbar\omega_2 j$$

This yields:

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{d[(E_{ik} + \hbar\omega_2 j) n_{ijk}]}{dt} = \\ & = k_{10} \hbar\omega_2 j \{ (j + 1) n_{ij+1k} - j n_{ijk} + K (j + 1) n_{ij-1k} - K (j + 2) n_{ijk} \} + \\ & + k_{10} E_{ik} \{ (j + 1) n_{ij+1k} - j n_{ijk} + K (j + 1) n_{ij-1k} - K (j + 2) n_{ijk} \}, \quad j > 0 \\ & \frac{d[E_{ik} n_{i0k}]}{dt} = k_{10} E_{ik} [n_{i1k} - 2K n_{i0k}] \end{aligned}$$

After that the sum of the equations above over $\sum_{i,j,k=0}^{\infty}$ is calculated.

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{d \left[\sum_{i,j,k=0}^{\infty} (E_{ik} + \hbar\omega_2 j) n_{ijk} \right]}{dt} = \\ & = k_{10} \hbar\omega_2 \sum_{i,k=0}^{\infty} \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \{ j (j + 1) n_{ij+1k} - j^2 n_{ijk} + K j (j + 1) n_{ij-1k} - K j (j + 2) n_{ijk} \} + \\ & + k_{10} E_{ik} \sum_{i,k=0}^{\infty} \left[\sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \{ (j + 1) n_{ij+1k} - j n_{ijk} + K (j + 1) n_{ij-1k} - K (j + 2) n_{ijk} \} + n_{i1k} - 2K n_{i0k} \right] \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

The sum:

$$\sum_{i,j,k=0}^{\infty} (E_{ik} + \hbar\omega_2 j) n_{ijk} = E_{vibr}$$

is the total vibrational energy.

Calculation of the last sum of equation (10). First:

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} [(j+1)n_{ij+1k} - jn_{ijk}] + n_{i1k} &= \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} (j+1)n_{ij+1k} - \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} jn_{ijk} + n_{i1k} = |j' = j+1| = \\ &= \sum_{j'=2}^{\infty} j' n_{ij'k} + n_{i1k} - \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} j n_{ijk} = \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} j n_{ijk} - \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} j n_{ijk} = 0 \end{aligned}$$

Second:

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} [(j+1)n_{ij-1k} - (j+2)n_{ijk}] - 2n_{i0k} &= \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} (j+1)n_{ij-1k} - \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} (j+2)n_{ijk} - 2n_{i0k} = \\ &= |j' = j-1, j = j'+1| = \sum_{j'=0}^{\infty} (j'+2)n_{ij'k} - \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} (j+2)n_{ijk} - 2n_{i0k} = \\ &= \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} (j+2)n_{ijk} - \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} (j+2)n_{ijk} = 0 \end{aligned}$$

That is, the last sum in (10) equals zero, and the whole equation (10) can be re-written as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dE_{vibr}}{dt} &= k_{10} \hbar\omega_2 \sum_{i,k=0}^{\infty} \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} [j(j+1)n_{ij+1k} - j^2 n_{ijk}] + \\ &+ k_{10} \hbar\omega_2 K \sum_{i,k=0}^{\infty} \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} [j(j+1)n_{ij-1k} - j(j+2)n_{ijk}] \quad (11) \end{aligned}$$

Calculation of the first sum of (11):

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} [j(j+1)n_{ij+1k} - j^2 n_{ijk}] &= \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} j(j+1)n_{ij+1k} - \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} j^2 n_{ijk} = |j' = j+1, j = j'-1| = \\ &= \sum_{j'=1}^{\infty} (j'-1)j' n_{ij'k} - \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} j^2 n_{ijk} = \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} [(j-1)j - j^2] n_{ijk} = - \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} j n_{ijk} = - \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} j n_{ijk} \end{aligned}$$

Calculation of the second sum of (11):

$$\begin{aligned}
\sum_{j=1}^{\infty} [j(j+1)n_{ij-1k} - j(j+2)n_{ijk}] &= \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} j(j+1)n_{ij-1k} - \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} j(j+2)n_{ijk} = \\
&= |j' = j-1, j = j'+1| = \sum_{j'=0}^{\infty} (j'+1)(j'+2)n_{ij'k} - \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} j(j+2)n_{ijk} = \\
&= \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} [(j+1)(j+2) - j(j+2)]n_{ijk} = \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} (j+2)n_{ijk}
\end{aligned}$$

Substituting the results back into (11) yields:

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{dE_{vibr}}{dt} &= -k_{10}\hbar\omega_2 \sum_{i,k,j=0}^{\infty} jn_{ijk} + k_{10}\hbar\omega_2 K \sum_{i,k,j=0}^{\infty} (j+2)n_{ijk} = \\
&= k_{10}K E_{vibr-2} + 2k_{10}\hbar\omega_2 KN - k_{10}E_{vibr-2} \tag{12}
\end{aligned}$$

Here:

$$E_{vibr-2} = \sum_{i,k,j=0}^{\infty} \hbar\omega_2 j n_{ijk}$$

is the total vibrational energy stored in the mode v_2^l , and

$$N = \sum_{i,k,j=0}^{\infty} n_{ijk}$$

is the total number density of molecules. The right hand side of equation (12) is transformed as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
k_{10}K E_{vibr-2} + 2k_{10}\hbar\omega_2 KN - k_{10}E_{vibr-2} &= k_{10} [2\hbar\omega_2 KN - (1-K) E_{vibr-2}] = \\
= k_{10} (1-K) \left[\frac{2\hbar\omega_2 KN}{1-K} - E_{vibr-2} \right] &= k_{10} \left(1 - e^{-\frac{\hbar\omega_2}{T}} \right) \left[\frac{2\hbar\omega_2 N e^{-\frac{\hbar\omega_2}{T}}}{1 - e^{-\frac{\hbar\omega_2}{T}}} - E_{vibr-2} \right] = \\
&= k_{10} \left(1 - e^{-\frac{\hbar\omega_2}{T}} \right) \left[\frac{2\hbar\omega_2 N}{e^{\frac{\hbar\omega_2}{T}} - 1} - E_{vibr-2} \right]
\end{aligned}$$

The first term in the parenthesis is E_{vibr-2} at thermal equilibrium with temperature T , see e.g. [3], Eq. (49.3) there (taking into account that the level v_2^l is double degenerate). Equation (12) is transformed to its final form:

$$\boxed{\frac{dE_{vibr}}{dt} = k_{10} \left(1 - e^{-\frac{\hbar\omega_2}{T}} \right) [E_{vibr-2}^{eq}(T) - E_{vibr-2}]} \tag{13}$$

$$E_{vibr-2}^{eq}(T) = \frac{2\hbar\omega_2 N}{e^{\frac{\hbar\omega_2}{T}} - 1}, \quad E_{vibr-2} = \sum_{i,k,j=0}^{\infty} \hbar\omega_2 j n_{ijk}$$

$$E_{vibr} = \sum_{i,j,k=0}^{\infty} (\hbar\omega_1 i + \hbar\omega_2 j + \hbar\omega_3 k) n_{ijk}, \quad N = \sum_{i,k,j=0}^{\infty} n_{ijk}$$

Equation (13) is analog to Eq. (19-17') in [1].

Equation (13) can be readily integrated when the distribution of vibrational states is close to Boltzmann with temperature T_{vibr} . At constant N the energy quantities can be replaced by their specific values per molecule. That is:

$$E_{vibr-2} = \frac{2\hbar\omega_2}{e^{\frac{\hbar\omega_2}{T_{vibr}}} - 1}, \quad E_{vibr-2}^{eq} = \frac{2\hbar\omega_2}{e^{\frac{\hbar\omega_2}{T}} - 1}$$

and:

$$\frac{dE_{vibr}}{dt} = \frac{dT_{vibr}}{dt} \frac{dE_{vibr}}{dT_{vibr}} = c_v^{vibr} \frac{dT_{vibr}}{dt}$$

where c_v^{vibr} is the vibrational heat capacity. For the linear oscillators, see e.g. [3], Eq. (49.4) there:

$$c_v^{vibr} = c_1 + c_2 + c_3$$

$$c_{1,3} = \frac{(\hbar\omega_{1,3})^2 \exp\left(\frac{\hbar\omega_{1,3}}{T_{vibr}}\right)}{T_{vibr}^2 \left[\exp\left(\frac{\hbar\omega_{1,3}}{T_{vibr}}\right) - 1\right]^2}, \quad c_2 = \frac{2(\hbar\omega_2)^2 \exp\left(\frac{\hbar\omega_2}{T_{vibr}}\right)}{T_{vibr}^2 \left[\exp\left(\frac{\hbar\omega_2}{T_{vibr}}\right) - 1\right]^2}$$

The transformed equation (13) reads:

$$\frac{dT_{vibr}}{dt} = k_{10} \frac{\left(1 - e^{-\frac{\hbar\omega_2}{T}}\right)}{c_v^{vibr}(T_{vibr})} \left[E_{vibr-2}^{eq}(T) - E_{vibr-2}(T_{vibr})\right] \quad (14)$$

References

- [1] Herzfeld K F and Litovitz T A 1959 *Absorption and dispersion of ultrasonic waves* (New York: Academic Press)
- [2] Kotov V 2020 *J. Phys. B* **53** 175104
- [3] Landau L and Lifshitz M 1980 *Course of Theoretical physics, vol. 5, Statistical physics. Part 1* (Butterworth-Heinemann)